

Ewing Sarcoma, an Update on Molecular Pathology with Therapeutic Implications

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Abstract

Ewing sarcoma is a developmental tumor characterized by balanced chromosomal translocations and formation of new fusion genes. Despite the large amount of knowledge regarding the molecular aspects obtained in the last few years, many questions still remain. This article focuses on research on the molecular pathology and possible developments in targeted therapies in this malignancy and discusses some related bottlenecks, as well as the possible role of pathologists, the availability of samples, the lack of appropriate animal models, and the resources needed to carry out preclinical and clinical research